

Simulation of a Neural Network Model Identification Algorithm

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Abstract. An algorithm developed based on a multi-layer neural network with learning is proposed for discriminating deterministic functions in the presence of random distortions and under the conditions of both parametric and non-parametric a priori uncertainty. Statistical simulation methods help to establish its operability and sufficiently high efficiency. The conditions for the expediency of its application in practical applications are stated. #CSOC1120

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1 Introduction

One of the important tasks of modern science and technology is the construction and verification of a mathematical model that describes the relationship of various parameters of the process or phenomenon under study [1], [2]. From the analytical point of view, for setting a model, it is enough to establish the type of functional dependence between the analyzed quantities that determines the structure of the model. The issue of compliance of the real situation with the established dependence is usually solved by experimental or statistical methods. For example, to find out which of the available mathematical dependencies is more consistent with the observed data, one can apply either the Bayesian method [3] or the maximum likelihood method [4], [5]. However, for their practical implementation, these approaches require a certain amount of a priori information, which is often absent. In addition, their application encounters significant difficulties in the presence of nonparametric uncertainty.

In this paper, to overcome these limitations, a model identification algorithm is proposed, which is implemented using neural network technologies. For clarity, it is assumed that the task of discrimination is reduced to choosing one of two possible functional dependencies. Statistical simulation methods are used to estimate the performance and efficiency of the introduced algorithm.

2 Problem Statement

Let $f_0(t)$ and $f_1(t)$ be the distinguishable functions. Then it is assumed that the realization of the random process $\xi(t)$ is available for observation, which is an additive mix of the Gaussian white noise $n(t)$ with the one-sided spectral density (intensity) N_0 and one of the functions $f_i(t)$, $i=0,1$ introduced above.

From the point of view of the statistical decision theory [6], the model identification can be reduced to the problem of discriminating between the signals described by the functions $f_0(t)$ and $f_1(t)$. Thus, the realization of the observed data can be represented as

$$\xi(t) = \theta f_1(t) + (1 - \theta) f_0(t) + n(t). \quad (1)$$

Here θ is a discrete parameter that can take two values: $\theta=1$, if the useful signal is described by the function $f_1(t)$, and $\theta=0$, if the useful signal is described by the function $f_0(t)$. Based on (1), it is required to decide which of the two signals is present in the observed realization. This is equivalent to choosing a mathematical model that describes the observed data. The a priori probabilities p_0 and p_1 of the presence of the functions $f_0(t)$ and $f_1(t)$, respectively, are assumed to be known, as well as that $p_0 + p_1 = 1$. In the particular case of the equiprobable appearance of $f_0(t)$ and $f_1(t)$, one gets

$$p_0 = p_1 = 0.5. \quad (2)$$

The optimal algorithms for discriminating signals are described and studied in sufficient detail in the well-known works [6], [7]. This makes it possible to compare the discrimination quality achieved when using statistical and neural network approaches. It is noteworthy that the task of discriminating signals can be formulated in terms of testing statistical hypotheses. We call the case the hypothesis H_0 when the realization (1) contains the function $f_0(t)$ (with $\theta=0$), and when the realization (1) contains the function $f_1(t)$ (with $\theta=1$) it is the hypothesis H_1 . Then the probabilities

$$p_0 = P(H_0) = P(\theta=0), \quad p_1 = P(H_1) = P(\theta=1)$$

are called the a priori probabilities of the corresponding hypotheses. In the particular case when $f_0(t) = 0$ the discrimination task is reduced to the task of the signal detection against the background of the white noise.

Due to the presence of noise, the decision made in favor of one or another hypothesis cannot be error-free. In this regard, to solve the discrimination problem, it is necessary to set an optimality criterion, taking into account what errors may occur. The decision made is denoted by γ . When $\gamma=0$, the decision is made in favor of the hypothesis H_0 , and when $\gamma=1$, it is made in favor of the hypothesis H_1 .

Firstly, the error probabilities that characterize the efficiency of one or another processing algorithm are considered.

1) The type I error probability when a decision is made in favor of the hypothesis H_1 , but in fact the hypothesis H_0 appears to be fair:

$$\alpha = P(H_1|H_0) = P(\gamma = 1 | \theta = 0), \quad (3)$$

that is, that decision is made that there is the signal $f_1(t)$ in the observed data (1), while the signal $f_0(t)$ is received. In the problem of signal detection, such a situation is called a false alarm, and the quantity α is called the false alarm probability.

2) The type II error probability when a decision is made in favor of the hypothesis H_0 , but in fact the hypothesis H_1 is fair:

$$\beta = P(H_0|H_1) = P(\gamma = 0 | \theta = 1), \quad (4)$$

that is, that decision is made that there is the signal $f_0(t)$ in the observed data (1), while the signal $f_1(t)$ is received. In the problem of the signal detection, such situation is described as the signal missing, and the quantity β is the missing probability here.

3) The average error probability:

$$p_e = p_0\alpha + p_1\beta. \quad (5)$$

For most of the optimality criteria, the decision algorithm requires the generation of the likelihood ratio Λ or its logarithm L , with its subsequent comparison with the threshold [6], [7]:

$$L = \ln \Lambda = \frac{2}{N_0} \left[\int_0^T \xi(t) (f_1(t) - f_0(t)) dt \right] - \frac{E_1 - E_0}{N_0} \underset{H_0}{\overset{H_1}{>}} \ln h. \quad (6)$$

Here $E_1 = \int_0^T f_1^2(t) dt$, $E_0 = \int_0^T f_0^2(t) dt$ are the squares of the norms of the discriminated functions, coinciding in meaning with the signal energy, h is the threshold chosen in accordance with the accepted optimality criterion. For example, when using the Ziegert-Kotelnikov criterion [6], [7],

$$h = p_0/p_1 \quad (7)$$

and while using the maximum likelihood criterion [6], [7], one gets $h=1$ etc. In many cases of practical importance, the norms of the discriminated functions are the same, i.e.

$$E_0 = E_1 = E. \quad (8)$$

Then the expression (6) is simplified and takes the form

$$L = \ln \Lambda = \frac{2}{N_0} \left[\int_0^T \xi(t) (f_1(t) - f_0(t)) dt \right] \begin{matrix} > \\ < \end{matrix} \begin{matrix} H_1 \\ H_0 \end{matrix} \ln h. \quad (9)$$

The quality of the discrimination algorithm (9) has been studied in [6], [7], where analytical expressions for the error probability (3), (4) and the average error probability (5) are presented. In particular, when (2) and (8) are satisfied, one gets

$$p_e = 1 - \Phi\left(z\sqrt{(1-r_s)/2}\right), \quad (10)$$

where $\Phi(x) = \int_{-\infty}^x \exp(-u^2/2) du / \sqrt{2\pi}$ is the probability integral, $r_s = \int_0^T f_1(t)f_0(t) dt / E$ is the scalar product (correlation coefficient) of the functions $f_0(t)$ and $f_1(t)$ that characterizes the degree of their similarity,

$$z^2 = 2E/N_0 \quad (11)$$

is the power signal-to-noise ratio (SNR).

Now one selects the functions to be discriminated. One of them describes the model of the linear growth of the form

$$f_0(t) = A_0(b_0 + kt/T) \quad (12)$$

while another is the model of the exponential saturation

$$f_1(t) = A_1[b_1 - \exp(-at/T)]. \quad (13)$$

The parameters of the models k , a determine the growth rate of the functions, and the parameter b_i , $i=0,1$ is the initial value for the corresponding model. In this case, the amplitude factors A_0 , A_1 are selected so that the discriminated signals have the same norms, namely:

$$A_0 = A\sqrt{b_0^2 + kb_0 + k^2/3},$$

$$A_1 = A\sqrt{2a/[4b_1 \exp(-a) - \exp(-2a) - 4b_1 + 2ab_1^2 + 1]}.$$

Then the norms of the signals (12), (13) are

$$E_1 = E_0 = E = A^2T. \quad (14)$$

In Fig. 1, one can see the examples of the discriminated functions (12), (13) at $A=1$, $k=1$, $b_0=1$, $b_1=2$, $a=2$. The solid line corresponds to the $f_0(t)$ model and the dashed one – to the $f_1(t)$ model.

Fig. 1. The example of the discriminated models

3 Simulation of the Neural Discrimination Algorithm

Now it is time to carry out the simulation of the discrimination of signals (12) and (13) by a neural network. Then, the network inputs are supplied with time samples

$$\xi_i = \xi(t_i), \quad t_i = i\Delta t, \quad i = 1, \dots, N \quad (15)$$

of the observed realization $\xi(t)$ taken at short time intervals Δt .

Obviously, it is not possible to generate the samples $n_i = n(t_i)$ of white noise due to its infinite dispersion (average power). In this regard, since the dispersion of any real process is limited, as an interference model instead of white noise, one uses a broadband Gaussian random process with the same intensity and the maximum frequency in the spectrum, chosen in accordance with the Nyquist-Shannon-Kotelnikov theorem as follows: $f_{\max} = 1/2\Delta t$. Therefore, the transition to discrete samples of the signal and noise involves limiting the spectrum to the maximum frequency f_{\max} . The bandlimited noise then has the dispersion [6]

$$\sigma^2 = N_0 \omega_{\max} / 2\pi = N_0 f_{\max} = N_0 / 2\Delta t.$$

From here, after substituting the values of the spectral density $N_0 = 2\Delta t \sigma^2$ and the signal power (14) into (11), one gets for SNR

$$z^2 = E / \sigma^2 \Delta t = A^2 T / \sigma^2 \Delta t. \quad (16)$$

Thus, while carrying out the simulation, it is necessary to generate the number of samples $N = T / \Delta t$ that fit into the duration of the observation interval. This value is

set equal to 1024, and the following relationship between SNR, signal amplitude and noise dispersion is produced:

$$z^2 = A^2 N / \sigma^2 . \quad (17)$$

To set the required SNR, the signals with the unit amplitude $A = 1$ are to be generated, and the mean-square deviation of the noise samples are to be calculated according to (17) as $\sigma = \sqrt{N} / z$.

The structure of the selected neural network is shown in Fig. 2 [8]. The networks of a similar design are used in image classification [9]. The network consists of five layers. The first layer is convolutional. Its functioning is similar to the signal transformation by a linear filter, the pulse response of which is related to the synaptic weights of neurons and changes during the learning process. The samples of the observed realization (15) are fed to the input of the convolutional layer. There should be denoted the number P of inputs and synaptic coefficients of each neuron ($P < N$), also called the size of the kernel. The convolutional layer as a whole contains a certain number Q of filters, the pulse responses of which having the length of P samples are initially set by random numbers uniformly distributed over the interval $[0, 1]$, and they change during training. The filter responses to the input action are called feature maps. In this study, the convolutional layer with $Q = 32$ filters and the kernels having the size of $P = 32$ samples is chosen. Schematically, the operation principle of the convolutional layer is shown in Fig. 3.

The output of this layer contains $NQ = 1024 \cdot 32$ samples represented as the tensor with the dimension $N \times Q$. The second layer is the thinning layer selecting the maximal of the two adjacent samples and passing it to the output. Thus, the dimension of the input tensor is reduced to 512×32 samples. The Flatten layer flattens the tensor into one long vector having the size of $512 \times 32 = 2^{14} = 16384$ elements. The densely-connected layers consist of the neurons, to the inputs of which all the magnitudes from the previous layer arrive. The first of the densely-connected layers contains 128 neurons, while the second contains only two neurons.

All the neurons of the convolutional and second-to-last layers have a ReLU activation function of the form $F(x) = \max(0, x)$. The last layer is based on the Softmax activation function. This means that the output signal of the neuron y_i is subjected to the following transformation:

$$G_i = \exp(y_i) / \sum_{j=1}^n \exp(y_j).$$

On the one hand, it allows interpreting the output signals of the last layer as the estimates of the probabilities of the presence of each of their signals in the received realization, and, on the other hand, one can use the Cross-Entropy Loss Function as an objective function.

The neural network was trained based on 100,000 marked-up realizations of the mixes of the signals (12) and (13) with noise. After training, statistical simulation of the discrimination algorithm operation followed. A realization of the mix of one signal with noise was generated, and the output signals of the network were calculated. In the case of an incorrect decision, the error of the 1st or 2nd kind was recorded.

Fig. 2. The structure of the neural network

Fig. 3. The operation principle of the convolution layer

Fig. 4. The average error probability of discriminating between the models of the linear growth and the exponential saturation

The results of the neural network discrimination algorithm operation simulation are shown in Fig. 4. The theoretical dependence of the average error probability on SNR (16) is also shown here. The solid curve is calculated by the formula (10) and it characterizes the quality of the discrimination of the algorithm (9) using the Ziegert-Kotelnikov criterion with a threshold (7) and equal signal energies (14) and a priori probabilities (2). The circles demonstrate a similar mean probability of discrimination error when using the neural network algorithm.

From Fig. 4, it follows that the neural network algorithm is somewhat inferior in efficiency to the algorithm (6). However, unlike the algorithm (6), it can be used in when the signal shape, as well as the signal and noise parameters, are a priori unknown.

4 Conclusion

In the presence of complete a priori information regarding the characteristics of the received signals and background noise, to discriminate signals, there should be used a decision rule based on comparing the logarithm of the likelihood ratio functional with the threshold selected in accordance with the accepted optimality criterion. However, in the case when the shape of the discriminated signals and/or the background noise parameters are unknown, the efficiency of this discrimination algorithm may significantly reduce. In this case, it is advisable to use the discrimination algorithm generated with the help of a neural network. With appropriate training of the latter, the algorithm remains operable under the conditions of complete a priori uncertainty about the characteristics of discriminated signals and noise without a noticeable loss in performance.

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